

Assessment of School Facilities on Basic Science Teaching among Secondary School Teachers in Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The study focused on assessment of school facilities on Basic Science teaching among secondary school teachers in Abuja, Nigeria. The population of the study consists of all Basic Science Teachers in both public and private secondary schools in Abuja, during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample size consists of 174 (94 urban and 80 rural) teachers selected using multistage sampling technique. Three research questions and one hypothesis were raised. Two instruments titled: School Facilities Functionality Inventory Scale (SFFIS) and School Facilities Adequacy Inventory Scale (SFAIS) with reliabilities coefficient value of 0.787 and 0.902 were used respectively. The draft instruments were subjected to validation process as three experts were involved in the validation of the instruments. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research questions and independent sample t-test to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings, showed that the level of availability of school facilities was high, functionality is poor, while adequacy is low. However, there is no significant difference in the influence of school facilities on basic science learning between rural and urban areas. It is therefore recommended that all hands are to be on deck in ensuring functionality adequacy of school facilities for basic science learning in both rural and urban schools.

Keywords: Assessment, School facilities, Basic science learning, Influence, Teachers

Introduction

Qualitative science education entails the provision of relevant school amenities that would garner its processes for effective service delivery. According to Mbaegbu, Unamma, Okorie, Ohuakanwa, Odupute, & Akpelu (2021), the poor performance in basic science resulted from remarkable lack of well-organized human resources, instructional materials and facilities in teaching and learning of basic science at the basic secondary education level. Availability of educational resources for teaching Basic Science in Junior secondary schools is seen as a life wire of the instructional process for successful learning outcomes of students. (Oni & Owolabi, 2021) The school facility consists of not only the physical structure and the varieties of building systems, such as mechanical, plumbing, electrical and power, telecommunications, security, and fire suppression systems. The facility also includes furnishings, materials and supplies, equipment and information technology as well as various aspects of the building grounds, namely, athletic fields, playgrounds, areas for outdoor learning, and vehicular access and parking. They are therefore, the physical and human resources that are used in the school in order to forestall effective teaching and learning.

Rufai, Umar and Idris (2013) as cited in Umar & Samuel (2019), asserted that students have low performance when they are not having access to standard facilities such as school library, laboratory and instructional equipment in the classrooms. An effective school facility is responsive to the changing programmes of educational delivery and at a minimum, should provide a physical environment that is comfortable, safe, secure, accessible, well illuminated, well ventilated, and aesthetically pleasing. A school without facilities may not be able to achieve the required goals and objectives of the educational system. This leads to a negative effect on students' academic performance. The school facility is much more than a passive container of the educational process: it is, rather an integral component of the conditions of learning. School facilities provide a real classroom experience for the learners and make teaching and learning process more interesting. The layout and design of a facility contributes to the place experience of students, educators, and community members.

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When facilities are available and skillfully utilizes, they influence learning and make it more meaningful. Gede and Tari (2011) as cited in Umar & Samuel (2019) noted that availability of resources in a school boost the morale of both teachers and learners towards effective delivery of lesson and one major factor contributing to academic performance in the schools' system. Depending on the quality of its design and management, the facility can contribute to a sense of ownership, safety and security, personalization and control, privacy as well as sociality, and spaciousness or crowdedness. In order to achieve good academic quality, these factors are pointed out as they relate to school facilities.

Practical lessons cannot be organized for science students in schools without science laboratories, or in schools with science laboratories but without the relevant materials and equipment. The only option for students in such schools who may wish to sit for science subjects in external examinations is the Alternative to Science's paper, whether or not the school building is adequately planned to accommodate the educational programme, it affects the life and activities that go on within it. The importance of school facilities has been highlighted by many educational administrators and planners. The importance attached to it as a vehicle for effective teaching and learning cannot be over emphasized (Saiyida in Sidhu, 2012), the importance of school plant was quoted thus: A school or a college is a vital and life-giving environment to the extent that it brings into the life of its students an abiding love and appreciation for all that is best and most significant in national and human life. Also, Oni (2020) claimed that the inadequacy of physical and material resources in schools is a major factor responsible for learning outcome of students. She further explained that schools that do not have adequate facilities such as workshops, laboratories, classrooms, teaching and learning materials are unlikely to post good results.

Saiyida in Sidhu (2012) asserts that as school heads and their academic staff plan and think together about the present and future needs of school facilities as vital factor that can contribute to the enrolment of students in the school. He further observes that through adequate planning of school facilities, they can determine the type of instructional materials teachers 'would need for effective instructions and whether the available classrooms are adequate for the anticipated number of students. Mgbodile (2000) cited in Osaigbovo & Osaigbovo (2021), stressing the need for school facilities, observed that the physical appearance and general condition of school physical facilities are the striking basis upon which many parents and friends of any educational institutions may make their initial judgments about the quality of what goes on in the school. In short, the physical facilities play a major role in determining the type of relationship between the school and the community. This is because parents and pupils make their judgments and take their decisions on whether to associate themselves with a particular school after a careful evaluation and consideration of the facilities in the school.

Ani (2007) cited in Osaigbovo & Osaigbovo (2021), while supporting the above statement, opined that if the quality and quantity of physical facilities attracts the admiration of a parent, the conviction of the parent will be that since the quality and quantity of facilities is of such level, the quality of the staff and school programme will be of high standard. Therefore, to attract the admiration and acceptance from the community, there is need for a well-planned school physical facilities and equipment. Assessment study on the availability and influence of school facilities, has being overlooked in the educational research in the basic education subsection. Therefore, this study sought to investigate assessment of school facilities on Basic Science teaching among secondary school teachers in Abuja, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study is to ascertain the degree of availability of school facilities and their influence on basic science learning, in two Area Councils (AMAC and Kuje) of FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

1. To ascertain the level of availability of school facilities used for basic science learning among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils.
2. To determine the level of functionality of school facilities used for basic science learning among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils.
3. To investigate the adequacy of school facilities used for basic science learning among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils.
4. To determine the influence of school facilities on basic science learning in rural and urban areas among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils.

Research questions

The following research question was raised in this study:

1. To what extent are school facilities for learning basic science available among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils in the sampled schools?

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2. To what extent are school facilities for basic science learning functional among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils. in the sampled schools?
3. To what extent are school facilities resources for basic science learning adequate among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils. in the sampled schools?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference of school facilities on basic science learning between Secondary School Teachers in Rural and Urban Areas

Methodology

This study was designed to assess availability, functionality and adequacy of school facilities and their influence on basic science learning. The study used adopted descriptive survey research design method. The population of the study comprised of basic science teachers in private and public owned primary and secondary schools during the 2022/2023 academic session in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) and Kuje area councils. The population was stratified into the two councils and then participants were purposively selected based on availability and willingness to participate in the study. A total of 174 (94 urban and 80 rural) basic science teachers in the selected two area councils (AMAC and Kuje) participated in the study. Two instruments titled: School Facilities Functionality Inventory Scale (SFFIS) and School Facilities Adequacy Inventory Scale (SFAIS) with reliabilities coefficient value of 0.787 and 0.902 were used respectively. The draft instruments were subjected to validation process as three experts were involved in the validation of the instruments. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research questions and independent sample t-test to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent are school facilities for learning basic science available among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils in the sampled schools?

Table 1: Availability of School Facilities for Learning Basic Science (N = 174)

S/N	ITEMS	AVAILABILITY				TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
		Yes		No			
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%		
1.	Basic Science Laboratory	11.9	68.4	55	31.6	174	100
2.	Adequate Furniture	142	81.6	32	18.4	174	100
3.	Well Ventilated Classrooms	152	87.4	22	12.6	174	100
4.	Dust Bins	146	83.9	28	16.2	174	100
5.	Well Equipped Library	108	62.1	66	37.9	174	100
6.	Basic science garden	70	40.2	104	59.8	174	100
7.	Computer laboratory	132	75.9	42	24.1	174	100
8.	Lightening/Electricity	135	77.6	39	22.4	174	100
9.	Toiletries	140	80.5	34	19.5	174	100
10.	Refrigerator	84	48.3	90	51.7	174	100

Table 1, above shows the extent to which school facilities for teaching basic sciences are available in the sampled schools. The result showed that in majority of the schools, eight (8) the ten (10) facilities were available. This is shown by the percentage of schools that claimed the eight facilities were available. Therefore, the following school facilities were available; basic science laboratory, adequate furniture, well-ventilated classrooms, dust bins, well equipped library, computer laboratory, lightening/electricity, toiletries. The following two facilities were however absent in majority of the schools sampled for the study; basic science garden and refrigerator.

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Research Question 2

To what extent are school facilities for basic science learning functional among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils. in the sampled schools?

Table 2: Functionality of School Facilities for learning Basic Science (N = 174).

S/N	ITEMS	FUNCTIONALITY						Total	%
		Poor		Fair		Very Okay			
		No	%	No	%	No	%		
1.	Basic science Laboratory	64	37.0	69	39.7	40	23.1	174	100
2.	Adequate furniture	28	16.1	83	47.7	63	36.2	174	100
3.	Well-ventilated classrooms	25	14.4	70	40.2	79	45.4	174	100
4.	Dust bins	28	16.1	79	45.4	67	38.5	174	100
5.	Well-equipped library	59	33.9	76	43.7	39	22.4	174	100
6.	Basic science garden	79	45.4	66	38.2	28	16.2	174	100
7.	Computer laboratory	48	27.6	81	46.6	45	25.9	174	100
8.	Lightening/ Electricity	49	28.2	51	29.3	74	42.5	174	100
9.	Toiletries	46	26.4	65	37.4	63	36.2	174	100
10.	Refrigerator	100	57.5	41	23.6	33	19.0	174	100

Table 2 above also showed the level of functionality of the school facilities for teaching basic sciences in the sampled schools. The functionality of the items was generally poor. For instance, it is only two of the facilities (Well ventilated classrooms and Lightening/ Electricity) that were very okay in more than 40% of the schools sampled. Five of the school facilities (Adequate Furniture, Well Ventilated Classrooms, Dust bins, Well Equipped Library and Computer Laboratory) were fair in more than 40% of the schools sampled. Two of the school facilities (Basic science garden and Refrigerator) were poor in more than 40% of the schools sampled. Therefore, the analysis result showed a poor functionality of the available equipment.

Research Question 3

To what extent are school facilities resources for basic science learning adequate among secondary school Teachers in Abuja Area Councils. in the sampled schools?

Table 3: Adequacy of School Facilities for Learning Basic Science (N = 174).

S/N	ITEMS	ADEQUACY						Total	%
		Not Adequate		Somewhat Adequate		Very Adequate			
		No	%	No	%	No	%		
1.	Basic science Laboratory	73	42.0	65	37.4	36	20.7	174	100
2.	Adequate furniture	47	27.0	74	42.5	53	30.5	174	100
3.	Well-ventilated classrooms	44	25.3	63	36.2	67	38.5	174	100
4.	Dust bins	38	21.8	75	43.1	61	35.1	174	100
5.	Well-equipped library	74	42.5	64	36.8	36	20.7	174	100
6.	Basic science garden	94	54.0	54	31.0	26	14.9	174	100
7.	Computer laboratory	62	35.6	70	40.2	42	24.1	174	100
8.	Lightening/ Electricity	60	34.5	45	25.9	69	39.7	174	100
9.	Toiletries	62	35.6	49	28.2	63	36.2	174	100
10.	Refrigerator	98	56.3	46	26.4	30	17.2	174	100

Table 3 above showed the level of adequacy of the school facilities for teaching basic sciences in the sampled schools. The adequacy of the facilities was generally below average. For instance, none of the school facilities was found adequate in

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more than 40% of the schools sampled. Three of the school facilities (furniture, dust bins and computer laboratory) were somewhat adequate in more than 40% of the schools sampled. Therefore, the analysis result showed that generally, the school facilities for basic science teaching were not very adequate.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference of school facilities on basic science learning between Secondary School Teachers in Rural and Urban Areas

Table 4: T-Test Analysis of Influence of school facilities on basic science learning in rural and urban areas.

LOCATION	N	MEAN	STD. DEVIATION	T	D.F.	SIG.(2TAILED)	REMARK
Urban	94	47.7204	6.74435	1.141	171	.255	NS
Rural	80	46.5125	7.16531				

Table 4 presents the t-test comparison of influence of school facilities on basic science learning in rural and urban areas. The t-test comparison showed that the difference in rural and urban influence of school facilities on basic science learning was not statistically significant. This is evident from the sig-2 tailed values that is greater than the 0.05 benchmark. Since any t-test comparison of means of two groups which is greater than the 0.05 benchmark signifies insignificant difference in influence of the two groups (urban and rural areas), it therefore follows that the difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that There is no significant difference of school facilities on basic science learning between Secondary School Teachers in Rural and Urban Areas is accepted. The values of the mean influence of urban and rural areas however showed that the influence of urban area is higher than that of their rural areas. Since the difference is not statistically significant, it cannot be generalised; it must have occurred due to sampling error.

Discussions of findings

The findings of this study, showed that the level of availability of most school facilities for basic science learning is high to a great extent. Few of the school facilities, however, were not available in most of the studied schools. The variation in the level of availability across schools may not be unconnected with the fact that the schools are owned by bodies that differ in financial capability as well as focus and passion. While some of the owners are buoyant financially, some are not. Also, while some are passionate about availability of school facilities, some may not. The finding contradicts Tekalign (2016), who in a study on science laboratory equipment in the teaching of science subjects revealed that, 33.33% of the high schools under study did not have science laboratories. The unavailability and inadequacy of science laboratory resources in the schools makes it difficult for teachers and students to cover some areas that require practical activities, and this obviously is bound to be a contributory factor to non-achievement of curriculum objectives.

The next finding showed that to a large extent there is poor functionality of available school facility equipment in basic science learning. This may be as a result of inadequate maintenance of school facilities. This result agrees with Musa (2014) who studied the evaluation of availability and maintenance of school facilities and reported that some of the facilities were inadequate, while some are not available at all. The ones available were not maintained and were only used occasionally which leads to poor functioning. It was basically revealed that, what was indicated as available by the respondents were mainly dilapidated structures and facilities begging for maintenance. Asiyai (2012), also reported that the maintenance carried out on school facilities were inadequate on majority of the facilities. The factors encouraging school facilities depreciation included excess pressure on available facilities and delayed maintenance amongst others.

Another finding also showed that generally, the school facility for basic science learning were not very adequate. Paucity of funds and economic hardship can be a possible explanation for the finding. This result is in agreement with Education Insight (2005) that discovered that inadequacy of facilities such as laboratory equipment pose a big challenge in many schools.

The test of hypothesis showed that the difference in the influence of school facilities in urban area is not significantly different from that of the rural areas. The possible reason could be a result of the impact of governments' intervention in the promotion of learning of sciences in schools.

Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed that degree of availability of school facilities for teaching and learning of basic science was high while functionality and adequacy were poor. Also, the differences in the effect of school facilities on basic science learning in urban and rural areas is not statistically significant and therefore not generalizable.

Recommendation

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

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1. More funds should be injected into the basic school system for the purpose of procuring more school facilities for teaching and learning of basic sciences.
2. The quality assurance section in the ministry of education should lay more emphasis on availability, functionalities and adequacy of school facilities that aid teaching and learning of basic science in their routine monitoring activities of both public and private basic schools.
3. School administrators should ensure availability, functionality and adequacy of school facilities for teaching and learning of basic science.
4. Curriculum planners, developers and designers should endeavour to include in the curriculum, activities that will enhance the use of school facilities in the teaching and learning of basic science.

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